

Sociology of Graft in Sierra Leone: A Foucault Cognizance

Mohamed Bangura ✉

*Lecturer One, Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of Sociology and Social Work,
University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College, Freetown, Sierra Leone*

Abstract

Imploring a Foucault cognizance to comprehending graft in Sierra Leone furnishes fascinating sociological inquiry of how primacy is at the mecca of this social curiosity. In Sierra Leone graft has dawned as the significant risk to impoverished folk's subsistence as it influences social domains of people. This sociological inquiry accommodates a refined discourse of how graft is fundamentally a snag of primacy. It utilizes commonplace social case constructions of existence in Sierra Leone to emphasize the commonness of primacy in the social discourse of graft. The sociological inquiry accommodates a social substructure for the evolution of the sociology of graft in Sierra Leone by debriefing how graft and primacy are presently devised as personal exploits without comprehending the expansive nexus of primacy and consequently it affects admittance and snub. The sociological inquiry argues that dislodging graft political leaders or bureaucrats is not adequate to liquidate destitution nonetheless what is essential is a rudimentary transformation of the connections of primacy deployed on asymmetrical or unfair social structures.

Keywords: *Sociology, Graft, Sierra Leone, Foucault, Cognizance.*

Suggested citation: Bangura, M. (2024). Sociology of Graft in Sierra Leone: A Foucault Cognizance. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(3), 60-70. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2024.1(3).05

Introduction

Graft in Sierra Leone has destructive impacts on the means of impoverished folks to acquire essential amenities. Social research on graft has leaned to concentrate on how politicians and bureaucrats utilize their locality to pile up riches. Furthermore an emerging domain of inquiry in trivial graft materializing in all quarters of communal and financial survival. Completely these manifestations of graft are elaborately associated to primacy. Graft can be mediated as inherently a trouble of primacy. This sociological inquiry utilizes Foucault's cognizance on primacy to stress how graft in all its shapes is elaborately connected domain to and practice of divergent manifestations of primacy. Customary social inquiries (Singh, 2021) interpret graft as the misuse of communal primacy for secret obtains which directs to an accompanist perspective of primacy. Such reasoning conceals the proximate and micro social particulars of primacy. In that vein sense, primacy is grasped as ownership, as object possessed by those in primacy. Embracing from Foucault primacy is not an object that can be possessed, but rather an object that exploits and distinct as such in an assertive approach; it is further a social system than an ownership. Primacy has to be recognized as a social pattern in which circulate of interactions are in which persons are the agencies of primacy, never has it indicated of social inquiry (Schmitz, 2022). This awareness of primacy consequently gifts an exceptional scrutiny of graft in which exclusively concentrating on reigning nobilities in Sierra Leone as 'custodians' of primacy conceals fascinating aspects into how a transformation in the dealings of primacy and not only a transformation of political leaders or bureaucrats is the finest of battling graft.

Graft is regularly portrayed as an egoistic operation which concerns the utilization of dominion for private obtains (Ottosen, 2023). Albeit constructing against sociology of graft in Sierra Leone the stress

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is on comprehending graft as a social preferably than personal fact. Inevitably a concentration on primacy stresses the social disposition of graft. Graft can be viewed barely as an intent practice prevailing in a void or gap, but as a social conduct whose interpretation requires to be grasped with authority to social connections (Kamsi et al, 2023). Primacy from a Foucault cognizance is also interpreted from a social connection approach which permits for an inquiry of graft as social conduct. In this direction the concentration is on the social establishments and not persons in comprehending the cradles, components and answers to the botheration of graft and its linkages from governments stemming a private, public and social structure. (Luna-Pla and Nicolas-Carlock).

Literature review

Graft alludes to a diverse of illegal or illicit engagements. Reaped from various scholars and social inquiries, there is no consent relating what embodies graft. The concise interpretation or discourse utilized by the World Bank is the perversion of government position, functions or finances for secret obtains or favors (Hartman, 2020). These interpretations are akin to that assumed by Transparency International, the dominant non-governmental organization in the universal anti-corruption aspiration which mentions that graft contains conduct on the side of functionaries in the public sector, whether political leaders or bureaucrats, wherein they inappropriately and illicitly amass wealth or their cronies, by the abuse of the government primacy committed to the aforementioned (Maes, 2023).

The above mentioned interpretations, nonetheless, never include the trouble of graft in the free enterprise. Based on African Development Bank, graft is the misuse of government or private position for individual obtains (Moumbark et al, 2023). There are numerous sorts of graft, including, pervasive, diminutive and covetous. This sociological inquiry is lodged to pervasive graft. Pervasive graft includes routes of wrongdoing that stretch topmost from the hush money gathering directions and structures rely on graft for their subsistence. It pervades the whole government or economy. In similar situations, graft engagements accumulate outside the government and over Sierra Leonean society. Pervasive graft indicates that unprofessional engagements are regularized or standardized with government liability, oddity and not the law (Manira, 2023). Pervasive graft discloses the absence or paucity of social integrity and norms in the society. Norms are attitudes that signify in conjunction with assurance, esteem, obligation, liability, objectivity, tenderness, frank, acceptable and unacceptable, genuine and false, between government dependence (Bergquist and Johansson, 2023). Pervasive graft is depicted by avarice, backing, cronyism, fraud, theft, misappropriation and extortion among others.

Especially significant to specify that what is absorbed graft in individual nation may not be reasoned so in another owing to cultural variations. For instance, in cultural Sierra Leone, an individual who utilizes his or her authorized status to acquire employments for his or her kinfolds is not predominantly reasoned unlawful. Customarily, he or she is singly performing what every faithful associate of an extended family is anticipated to achieve. He or she may possibly be reprimanded if he or she fails to conduct in this direction. Notwithstanding, in the situation of interpretations upwards, this is cronyism and favoritism, consequently monumental graft.

Subsequently previous social research, this sociological article interpret graft broadly as the abuse or misuse of statuses or funds of government by bureaucrats for secret obtains typically in divergent demonstration of the word.

Natural Influence Abstraction

To comprehend the natural influence as an imperative to an investigation of the pervasive graft in Sierra Leone necessitates an elucidation of what comprises it and a rationale of ground it is pivotal for the comprehending of pervasive graft and natural influence putrefy in cultural Sierra Leone.

(WeiB, 2024) gifts an extensive interpretation of natural influence as the scope of individuality traits and other magnitudes of human activity that permit political, financial and social structures to operate and stay operational additionally. Such magnitudes retain the social particulars and inquiry of the supremacy

of law, political consensus, a restrained toil, equal judicial systems, regard for human decency and the purity of social existence, support services and community cultural welfares.

Gil de Zuninga (2022) interprets the natural influence as the integrated collectively cluster of the favorable and adverse aspect or traits that interpret the individual as an outlandish human being and how these sway the sort of his or her engagements in the disparate circles of social existence. The natural influence has six crucial elements: liturgical fortune, ethical fortune, stunning fortune, manpower fortune, individual competence and natural potentials (Lee and Chung, 2022).

Individual conduct is referenced as sloppy influence in the generality of graft matters. If graft level is to be abated, individual influence ought to be special grasped, and the comprehension further considerably employed. The concentration of natural influence is about the growth of the social identity content of individuals who carry out the duties of the socio-politico, economic and cultural evolution of their communities. In no wise economy can progress if it fails to possess folks with the appreciative natural influence traits such as uprightness, loyalty and productiveness.

Natural influence structure was utilized by the inquiry structured based on dual central spectrums, with each spectrum possessing dual realms. The foremost spectrum is the “cohort” and it is interested with the subsequent dual realms: the “communal” realm (literacy and constitution affairs); and the “oversight” realm (defense, custom, drill, path and relation affairs). The other spectrum is the “jobholder” and it is linked with the subsequent dual realms: the “readiness” realm (practice and consciousness, learning obtainment and transformation of previous drill); and the “task” realm (jobholders performance and drills).

The preceding natural influence social structure contends that natural influence theorization constitutes cultural community, oversight, readiness (drill and consciousness) and duty, everyone which must be premised in the particular empirical framework of an accustomed society. In the graft social discourse, the natural influence debates the government utility ideals. It is unattainable and biased to request upright conduct from civil servants except they are intimated the primary norms or ethos they are anticipated to utilize to their job and where the restrictions of satisfactory conduct situate.

Primacy Linkage to Graft

Interpreting theories is a house crowded with debates. Privately the ambience of this research article interpretation of primacy and graft require to be ingrained within the socio-cultural webs. Primacy within the framework of this deliberation adopts from Foucault’s concepts on the model science of primacy. Considering Foucault, any inquiry of primacy must commence originating bottom, in the eclectic and dissipated model science of primacy...where it is practiced over folks alternately validated at the hub; scan the concrete drills of subduing alternately the objectives that direct endeavors at hegemony; and perceive that primacy disseminates via meshes alternately being utilized at specific directions (Poorghorban, 2023).

Primacy consequently has to be comprehended as radiate, substantiated and legislated. It cannot be comprehended as a focused at a nucleus or as an ownership as primacy is ubiquitous; not because it grabs all, nonetheless subsequently it derives from far and near. Although comprehending graft in Sierra Leone it is consequently significant to punctuate wherein primacy comprehended this path outstrips politics and is as a commonplace, submissive and apparent social phenomenon. In conceptualizing the eccentric nature of primacy, Foucault also gifts fascinating cognizance into wherein graft is not the conserve of democratic establishments but preferably it is indigenous in all affinities in cultural communities (Sekkat et al, 2024). Primacy and graft consequently require to be recognized ostensibly in the localities where it is employed. Primacy, theorized as a lace of kinships demands the inquiry of the kinships of persons who comprised an assertive challenge or trouble as such and thereafter supervised to formulate a social system in the shape of district primacy or social education. Procuring this to graft it signifies that graft as an affair of primacy is constructed via district webs.

In Sierra Leone graft is manifest in all bearings of social existence for instance recounts of hush money to traffic police, disbursing to get an employment or essential privileges such as driver's license or passport. It is the utilization and not only misuse of primacy that requires further sociological discourse in the Sierra Leonean ambience. The utilization of primacy as an arrangement of tactics can also be a direction of discourse for graft. Primacy can also be interpreted as utilization of technique and in the case construction of Sierra Leone; graft has been utilized as a subsistence approach by numerous in divergent ranks at the expense of the impoverished that constantly have to compensate more for several essential services. Graft is largely interpreted in this sociological inquiry as the deliberate faux pas or disregard of an accepted task, or the undue exercise of primacy, with the intention of obtaining some merit further or limited openly the individual. Similar interpretation when challenged permits for a commencing path to argue the theory as a sociological phenomenon. Stress on the correlation between primacy and graft also high spots the social facsimile of graft. By this the social researcher of the inquiry emphasizes how primacy systems and social engagements disseminate graft and its repercussions from one ancestry to the succeeding. Juvenile or immature folks are socialized into a graft custom and assimilate social norms that treasure graft. Table one below highlights the various forms or of graft.

Table 1. Shades of Graft

Sorts of Graft	Interpretation	Includes
Administrative	Illicit Payments from clients for the implementation of existing regulations, policies and laws	A wide constituency experienced by citizens as harassment in their effort to obtain even small administrative goods.
Petty Graft	Small acts, or rent-taking actions, by civil servants.	Bribes for expediting documents or not charging suspect,
Graft	Gifts	Resources interchangeably with graft.
Influencing	Forcing a decision in one's favor	Political lobbying, secret contracts
Bureaucratic Graft	Patronage	Wide constituency with money
Political Graft	Misuse of entrusted power by political leaders.	Perpetuate one's position.
Government Capture	Payments and capture of jurisdiction	Sidelined Public Interest
Lofty Threshold	Misuse of lofty office for group or private obtain	Grand or Endemic Graft

Methodology

Social researchers nationally consent that empirical research on the subject matter of graft presents numerous demurrers. The barriers to the collecting of thoughtfully authentic or realistic social data involve: the anonymity that envelopes practically all graft operations; obliteration of dossiers and further fashions of prosecuting corroboration by the offenders; and panic of exploitation by prospective collaborators, to indicate but an inconsiderable. What appears to be the holistic social practice between most Sierra Leonean social pundits, who examined graft, is to haunt to perception inquiries, judicature or tribunal accounts and editorial diaries as an option wellsprings of social data. This sociological inquiry is no rarity on this detail.

The social inquiry exploited the qualitative methodology that coalesce consequent and principal data. Consequent data were obtained from the Parliament of Sierra Leone, Sierra Leone Anti-Corruption Commission: 2021, 2022 and 2023 Auditor-General recounts, 2022 and 2023 Transparency International recounts and other editorial diaries. Communal newspapers such as Standard Times, Awoko, Global Times, the Satellite, the Sierra Leone Independent and the Financial Gazette were also facilitative fountains of social data. Principal social data were collected via detail sessions handled with the ensuing: One Commissioner of the Sierra Leone Anti - Corruption Commission, Two Public Accounts Committee Members of Parliament and One Honorable Member of Parliament, Two Academics, One Policy and Research Official with Transparency International, and Two Officials from Citizens Trust. They were questioned on their insights concerning causes or generates of graft, effectiveness or

productiveness of the existing mitigation or moderation strategies, what must be done and the natural influence theory.

Spectrum and Nature of Graft in Sierra Leone

Graft has become part of commonplace social existence impeding Sierra Leone National Integrity Systems. Based on the 2023 Transparency International Corruption Perceptions Index, Sierra Leone ranks joint 108 out of 180 nations and scores 35 out of 100. Nonetheless there is a dissention over the utilization of this index; graft stays a notable worry swaying the Sierra Leonean economy. Based on same (2023) report 52% of Sierra Leoneans have paid a bribe to a service provider. Abdulai (2023) delivers a comprehensive discourse of graft in Sierra Leone illuminating how the political bureaucrats have frequently utilized their primacy to amass riches without aftermaths. Based on Abdulai this is because Sierra Leone governments overtime have consistently shielded corrupt officials who are certainly compensated with elevations.

Graft has assisted the establishment and preservation of customary consanguine Sierra Leonean regimes. In customary consanguine regimes, the head conserves primacy via individual civility, alternately via dogma or statute. Nevertheless associations of allegiance and reliance permeate an official diplomatic and governmental structure and leaders immerse bureaucratic positions diminutive to discharge public service than to amass individual riches and social status. The discrepancy between private and public concerns is deliberately clouded and individual networks comprise the bedrock and communal minaret of political structures.

Abdulai believes that the sort of cultural graft transformed into a civility orderliness which was vehemently supported by political bureaucrats. Political bureaucrats utilize their access to resource to construct political colonies and allegiance to plunder.

For instance, a combine inquiry conducted by the Sierra Leone Center for Accountability and Rule of Law, Public Financial Management Consortium, the United Kingdom's department for International Development (DFID) and Christian Aid (UK) estimated that in 2020 alone Sierra Leone lost 15.9 Trillion Leones to graft. A quartet inquiry that argue that Sierra Leonean political bureaucrats perceive politics as a shot for acquiring riches instead of assisting poor folks. Political graft is consequently an actuality of Sierra Leonean socio-economic context. This has further evolved into a civility structure in which allegiance to the political colony is compensated by defense to prosecution. Corruption has become orthodox within Sierra Leonean social systems. It is a matter of integrating of the aberrant and acknowledging that the codes of the match require privileges, hush money, and fleeing.

Primacy Dynamics

Sierra Leone has since independence in 1961 incrementally become a consanguine nation lodged on the authority of government structures to ensure consistent grab on primacy by one political entity. In such a framework the utilization of communal chaos, political intimidation and police brutality become a significant section of commonplace existence. Sierra Leone since 1967 has been marred by political indifference, violence, intimidation, economic implosion, food insecurity and holistic anxiety. In numerous paths this crisis was an inescapable catapult of unsettled and deep-seated resource and tribal differences; nevertheless it has been engulfed by All Peoples Congress Party and Sierra Leone Peoples Party usual desperate battle to retain primacy. There was a sudden legitimatization of primacy in what Arif and Dutta (2024) refers the resuscitation of the protective commune of governance.

Had Sierra Leone Peoples Party lost primacy in 1996, senior National Provisional Ruling Council officials would probably have been held responsible for a host of unresolved state affairs such as the Extra Judicial Killings of All Peoples Congress officials in Freetown, pivotal graft scandals of the 1990s, and the thieving of the War Victims Fund? Senior Sierra Leone People's Party bureaucrats nonetheless had an obvious concern in retaining primacy which obviously impacted Sierra Leone People Party's post 1996 tactics. The nature of the government transformed considerably during the late 1990s with the co-option of the

war veterans, peace keeping and the emerging impression of an impatient and radical empowerment alliance (Dyer and Gbla, 2022).

Etuk (2020) elucidate that this authoritarianism involved an internal reconfiguration of African politics and Sierra Leonean government politics leading to the emergence of domestic tyranny. The political bureaucrats has consequently evolved an elaborate pattern to guard their primacy and access to resource via a robust police state as well as passing legislations such as Public Order Act and Protection of Privacy Act enshrined in the 1991 constitution to guard themselves from communal scrutiny and dominate the proletariats. Admittance to political primacy is consequently significant to impress accomplishment in other socio-economic and socio-cultural spheres of communal existence in Sierra Leone.

Social Spaces: Foucault on Primacy and Graft

In Sierra Leone graft is pervasive in all socio-economic relationships. It has become institutionalized and part of commonplace social existence. This has had unfavorable impacts on the impoverished that currently have a tax levied even on free fundamental services such as acquiring a birth certificate, national identity card, driver's license, passport and others. Ensuing are varied sorts of the nature of graft, in which the model science of primacy bolster intimate how like primacy, graft is ubiquitous. The social constructions are meant to gift foundations of observations with graft which assist concretize the discourse that graft is about primacy. The observations are lodged in loosely and interwoven with conceptual discussions to further enlighten Foucault comprehension of primacy and the battle against graft from a national and international spectrum based on existing external organizations (Synman. 2022).

Political Graft

Some political bureaucrats in Sierra Leone have utilized their positions to amass vast riches. There are numerous instances of political bureaucrats alleged to involve in graft engagements. Below is an excerpt from an Anti-Corruption Commission press release on alleged graft involving Clerk of Parliament Honorable Paran Umar Tarawally and his wife?

“The Commission is investigating allegations that the Clerk of Parliament employed his wife without due process and that since the said employment, Mrs. Abibatu Tarawally has not been reporting for duties but received salaries. This raises serious questions of Conflict of Interest and abuse of position by the Clerk of Parliament” (Anti-Corruption Commission Sierra Leone, 2024).

Similarly in 2021 Sierra Leone's Anti – Corruption Commission (ACC) filed graft indictment against Paul Sobba Massaquoi, Executive Director of the Sierra Leone Maritime Administration and other members of the administration.

Political primacy in the rank or status was in this alleged matter significant in acquiring employment. The primacy is lodged in the rank or status and not the individual. This explicates why dislodging an official will not terminate graft rather the concentration must be on transforming institutional associations. It is inside these institutional associations that political primacy is employed as a technique to acquire riches.

Cronyism

Cronyism is the vast common social instance of how graft has been adopted as a path of existence in Sierra Leone. The practice of primacy to guarantee individual gratify relatives or comrades is broadly approved as a path of exploiting establishments at the cost of those who are outside such linkages. In such instances primacy is lodged in the social linkages that permit folks admittance to deliveries and mercies in unmerited paths. When primacy is perceived within the framework of associations and social asset it becomes obvious how it's further a technique than an ownership. Based on young folks in Sierra Leone you have to understand someone to get anything in this nation. Accessing a job or services is not easy without discovering whether you understand an individual who understands an individual at the establishment. Primacy of linkages permits folks to ignore distant lines, access hospitals or even access admissions at universities. Practically link to entirety which involves offers, employment agreements and

all posture of private and public deliveries and mercies demand alerting an individual who can pressure judgments in an individual's advantage. Giving hush money to functionaries is also concluded via linkages as linking them openly is insurmountable. Primacy comprehended via linkages of graft in this path "should be diagnosed as object which disseminates, or as object which only operates in the shape of a sequence...Primacy is exploited and practiced via a web association... Persons are the wagons of primacy, not its directions of inquiry" (Abdulai, 2023). Linkages envelop the entire society which generates graft immersed within commonplace connections. Graft and primacy are consequently not the ownership of single social class or a person conversely are eccentric. Although the potent are usually involved in lofty threshold of political graft impacting series of folks, graft is also practiced by the vast of the cultural folks in multiple directions and social spaces (Kovasevic, 2021).

Traffic Police and Bribes on the Road

"The Anti-Corruption Commission (ACC) is concerned about the findings of the Report launched by the coalition of civil society titled "Corruption stops with Us: Ending bribery for traffic offenses in Sierra Leone"; as it showcases the involvement of Sierra Leone traffic police officers in bribery and petty graft (Press Release).

Based on this report Traffic police on Sierra Leonean roads have utilized their position to acquire diminutive fortunes via bribes especially from public transport operators in urban areas known as Mini vans ('Poda-Podas'). Public transport operators are required to be registered transporters who have constant vehicle examinations and employing licensed drivers. As a result of economic difficulties numerous operators disobey the law and majority of the drivers are engaged in illicit driving engagements. A considerate graft network between the police and operators has surfaced in which they commit a routine charge to operate without the police halting them for the numerous offences they violate. In such scenario the police have primacy to apprehend the drivers and detain the vehicles. They utilize this primacy to ensure the operators commit the bribe. The operators have recognized that it is inexpensive to pay the police than it is to ensure their vehicles are road worthy or they have the imperative license to operate. This high spot the significance of discussing how primacy is practiced in particular relations where folks because of their ranks or status can impact the behavior of persons. Utilizing a Foucault approach, graft in this scenario can be comprehended as the discursive methods, models and instruments of government in this matter the police as part of government (Singh, 2022). Graft consequently becomes extant because of the primacy relation that happens between the Sierra Leone Police and motorists. This is not to express that primacy is something that one entity does to the other, it is alternately the economic space of controversy. Reason motorists at times initiate the bribes or jump ambush traffic charges at road checkpoints.

Results and Discussion

Graft is the awkward circumstance of all malfeasances of Sierra Leone. It is the sweeping essence. Money matters in Sierra Leone. Money and primacy matter. Money is primacy and primacy is money. These are unheard social maxims in the Sierra Leonean society. Money primacy gets folks positions even in the civil and security services. Money primacy easily gets folks educational certificates, diplomas and even degrees. Secondary school students are now assisted by their parents to pay for a fore knowledge of their examination questions or for help in the open examination room to pen their examination. All this is with the paid compromise of the tutors and supervisors. This is all occurring because graft has bulldozed the communal integrity structure. Folks have, nonetheless, lost trust in it. Even those who are paid to compromise it have lost trust in the structure. If money can take one where he or she desires to be top of the rung the better without effort and honestly for it, why disturb about the fake tagged communal morality, integrity, honesty, accountability and all that speaks about spiritual qualities, the potency of the moral status of Sierra Leone. This is not a surprise why Sierra Leone has been interpreted as pariah in the international commerce community and has been banned from grants and loans from international monetary institutions for educational, infrastructural, and other developments of which Sierra Leone is

in desperate demand. The threshold of development is, consequently, snail paced or brought to a total halt.

This is not a social revelation. Not a day passes without one or two or further encounters with one or two continual figure of faces of these morals settling disorder. Folks encounter graft at security check points, border posts, in hospitals, parastatals, government offices, private and commercial firms, manufacturing industries, and the educational institutions. These are just a minute of the locations an individual may encounter the hydra headed monster called graft. Sierra Leoneans seem to have accepted it as a path of social existence and the less the bother themselves about it.

Propositions

One of the consistent interrogations in graft inquiry is how the threshold of graft can be mitigated. Pragmatically, although there have been varied campaigns and policies administered in Sierra Leone, there is no obvious social evidence of decreasing likelihood in graft threshold. As carved in the Transparency International Graft Perception Index, combating graft is not a simple task. Some of the up for consideration involve communal consciousness, political will, supportive civil service conditions, natural influence as a significant instrument in battling systemic graft and communal sector oversight reconfigurations.

The communal demands to be schooled on the merits of good governance and engage in elevating it. The communal itself bears a host share of duty for insisting on integrity and honesty in government interactions. The communal requests to educate: (1) not to let anybody purchase their ballots; (2) not to commit bribes themselves; (3) to complaint incidents of graft to the authorities; (4) to school their wards the upright customs, for instance, that integrity is right and graft is wrong. Educating and including the communal in constructing integrity is pivotal to preventing graft via communal awareness, yearly broad-based national integrity seminars or conferences and investigative cultural journalism.

Political will is a crucial feature to evolve sustainable and robust anti-corruption programs. Without it, governmental steps fashioned to promote civil service, strengthen transparency and accountability, and have proved to be inefficient. The theory of political will calls to the actionable reliable purpose of political players to confront graft at a systemic threshold. The concentration must be on the players, their intentions and the options they construct to elevate and execute anti-corruption reforms. Battling graft has dissipation repercussions, which can recruit influential social forces to guard keen interests. Without political will, anti-corruption strategies may drown in inclement political oceans. Sierra Leone Anti-Corruption Commission, Auditor-General and Parliament lack primacy to propel their crafts when the political winds are very robust.

The lofty standards of ethical behavior anticipated of communal officials are one side of the coin. The other side is decent working and living conditions for the servants of the communal, consisting of adequate employment safety, privileges for promotion and even remuneration or social appreciation. If communal servants are underpaid, overlabored and unsafe, they are less likely to accept strategies to battle graft corruption. Consequently, engulfment of petty and accelerate graft.

Concentrating on prevention and improving structures by transforming social values, formulating a culture of vocationalism and learning, establishing sufficient remuneration and ensuring deterrence may yield favorable outcomes. Graft must be tagged to seem a lofty risk and small benefit engagement. The culture of transparency, accountability and the rule of law are vital to crushing graft.

Individuality traits and attitudes impact the path, which folks conduct their lives at homestead and at job. Individuality traits are intrinsic or learned at early stages of social existence. They are profound traits which interpret an individual and they are very constant and resistant to transformations. Traits such as violence, ambition and dominance may be reflections of individuality. Attitudes are acquired and perpetual inclinations or aptitudes, expected to react positively or negatively to folks, cultural associations, and decisions among others. A posture is an aptitude to react in a certain direction; the reaction is the

conduct itself. It is perceived that folk's attitudes gift some sort of cognitive association of the universe in which they dwell, permitting them to construct speedy decisions on what to do when encountering certain circumstances.

Graft is always an insignia of impoverished governance and feeble social structures. Battling Fighting graft should, nevertheless, envelop consistent reform of communal administration and social structures. Nations suffering from acute graft must face the problem in successive encounters. These involve: undertaking an extensive evaluation or examination of the scope, reasons and repercussions of graft; initiating reforms of the judicial, cultural, social, economic political structures in order to strengthen good governance; participatory civil society in a discourse about graft and including it in the growth of anti-graft methods.

Reconfiguring communal entity oversight and finance is also significant in the battle against graft, as privileges and incentives for graft are very much profoundly seated in communal entity oversight. . This means transforming the direction government does its transactions, that is, the inside oversight of communal resources and the administration must be reconfigured. The reconfigurations in the previous have not gone very far because they have not been appropriately thought via and supervised and have not yielded the wanted outcome of formulating a professionalized, effective, even and transparent civil service. In revolutionizing the civil service, there must be consideration for constructing a meritocracy civil service that is adequately remunerated, promoted transparency and accountability in financial oversight procedures, reconfigured sectorial service delivery and expand cultural decentralization with expansive accountability.

Conclusion

Graft in Sierra Leone requires to be recognized within a framework in which access to the most fundamental services is arbitrated by some sort of fraud and favoritism. Utilizing Foucault notion individuals can map an emerging sociology of graft established on deconstructing how numerous shapes of primacy are deployed as techniques to amass even at the most essential thresholds. From petty graft to great political scandal, it is probable to analyze how numerous shapes of primacy positioned in divergent relations are linked to graft. Primacy is not a belonging but an approach. If folks comprehend graft as the strategic deployment of primacy not only to amass but also as a subsistence system for instance matters of petty graft by subordinate threshold officials such as a teacher selling exam papers to students. Primacy like graft is a social procedure. It is not a thing that can be owned. Through such an analysis the research article has depicted how graft has to be comprehended as a social phenomenon. Graft has become normalize because of folk's acceptability of these engagements in the pretense of survival tactics.

Utilizing a selection of subject matters, the research article has high spotted how primacy comprehended as disperse assists in comprehending the pervasive nature of graft. The research article has gifted a landmark of evolving the sociology of graft in Sierra Leone. It argued that graft is a social issue and requires to be reasoned within commonplace associations of folks in cultural society. Individuals are incriminated in graft stains but they do not function isolation from society. Social inquiry of the model science of primacy within social contexts can furnish contemporary and fascinating paths of comprehending graft. The research wraps up that like primacy, graft is ubiquitous. It is not restricted to one stratum or cohort; it takes assorted shapes from common threshold petty graft to political graft. In all these instances primacy is lodged as a tactic to ensure betterment for persons. To confront graft there is necessitate recognizing that it is beyond removing or apprehending persons conversely regenerating social system that upgrades asymmetrical primacy interactions.

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